

WHY PRESERVE - A COLLABORATIVE WAY TO PROMOTE THE SECTOR

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Abstract - Advocating for digital preservation is not a one-time effort, it's a continuous journey that demands time, energy, and resources from those who often have the least to spare. Recognizing this challenge, the Digital Preservation Coalition has made 'Advocacy' one of its five core strategic priorities, underscoring its vital role in sustaining our digital legacy. To truly make an impact, we must communicate the value of digital preservation in ways that resonate with diverse audiences. While its importance to truth, memory, and cultural heritage is undeniable, preservation is not just about safeguarding the past. For many organizations, it's also about managing risk, complying with legal and regulatory frameworks, protecting reputations, and ensuring business continuity. These practical drivers can be powerful catalysts for action. Understanding *why* an organization chooses to invest in digital preservation is key. These motivations form the foundation for persuasive, tailored advocacy—messages that inspire action and secure long-term support. Whether in cultural heritage, academia, research, business, or law, identifying and articulating these reasons is a crucial step in every digital preservation strategy.

That's where the Why Preserve campaign comes in. This poster will describe a global initiative which invites digital preservation practitioners to reflect on their organization's unique motivations, share their stories, and transform

those insights into compelling advocacy messages. Launching alongside World Digital Preservation Day on Thursday, 6 November, and the iPRES 2025 conference, the campaign itself will spotlight the current landscape, outline the path forward, and invite the community to unite in answering a powerful question: *Why Preserve?*

Submission Type –Poster

Keywords – Collaboration, Community, education.

Conference Topics – Tūhono - Connect

I. INTRODUCTION

Advocacy. Outreach. Promotion. Education. Whatever the title used, explaining the importance of digital preservation and the work we do as practitioners is never easy. The lack of resources and budget many digital practitioners are working with means that it is hard to remember the reasons why we do what we do and it is even harder to find the reasons why the organisations we work for should invest in digital preservation. Organisations have different success factors, and, in some cases, it can be difficult to align the priorities and needs of the business with the resources required to carry out digital preservation work. It is also difficult to prioritise time to work on advocacy, internally or externally, when there is no guarantee of success.

Why Preserve is an advocacy campaign designed by the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) to remove some of the advocacy burden currently resting with digital preservation practitioners by providing a high-

level campaign that documents and educates on the importance of digital preservation. It aims to be a campaign that the entire sector can use for support with advocacy and championing their work with digital content.

This poster will be one part of a promotional strategy to launch the Why Preserve Campaign as the 2025 World Digital Preservation Day Theme. The poster will include details of the campaign and provide a range of ways for digital preservation practitioners at all levels and from all organisations to get involved. This paper will also provide a brief introduction to the current landscape, why a campaign is needed, and why we have chosen to launch it at iPRES.

I. THE CURRENT LANDSCAPE

- I. It cannot be denied that a range of resources that provide support with advocacy already exists across the sector. The DPC have published the Executive Guide to Digital Preservation¹ and the Business Case Toolkit² and the UK National Archive published their 'Plugged In, Powered Up' resources, which were designed to help archives advocate to build digital capacity.³ However, there are two issues with previously published resources. Firstly, many of them place additional work on digital preservation practitioners before they will be of use. For example, the DPC executive guide, as stated in its introduction,

"The Executive Guide on Digital Preservation provides practitioners with a combination of generic and specific messages and motivators designed to communicate with senior executives...with a view to embedding the value of digital preservation at the core of every organization."

All the ingredients are available to make a presentation or business case tailored to a specific organisation. However, feedback since the toolkit was published has shown that

¹See

<https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dpeg-home>

²See

<https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/business-case-toolkit>

³See,

<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/archives->

although digital practitioners can see the usefulness of the resource, they just don't have the capacity to add the work required to their to do list. The recently published 'Mental Health and Wellbeing in the Digital Preservation Community' report highlighted the advocacy burden as one of the main issues affecting mental health across the community, with 63% of respondents saying they felt overwhelmed by the advocacy burden.⁴

The Plugged In, Powered Up resources have a similar issue as they consist of content that can be added into presentations and papers. One leaflet in particular focuses on what digital practitioners can do to upskill, including taking training courses, taking time out of work to attend an archives school run by The National Archive and finding a mentor through the scheme that TNA offers.⁵ None of the outputs provided by the program can be used 'out of the box' to promote or advocate digital preservation. The Plugged In, Powered Up Resource is also an example of the second issue with currently available advocacy resources.

Plugged In, Powered Up was created by the UK National Archive in response to a need identified by the sector that help to increase digital capacity was required. These resources are well developed and have their place in the resource landscape. However, the resource is focused solely on the archive sector with no scalability to include the rest of the digital preservation community. In addition, overall digital capacity was the focus of the program, with digital preservation resources taking up only a small portion of the overall program output. Academic articles have been published which deal with advocacy in specific areas of the digital preservation sector, but none exist which cover

sector/our-archives-sector-role/plugged-in-powered-up/

⁴ <https://www.dpconline.org/docman/digital-preservation/mhw/3431-mhw23-report/file>, pg30

⁵ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/archives-sector/our-archives-sector-role/plugged-in-powered-up/peer-mentoring/>

the sector as a whole.⁶ This has led to a fractured sector in terms of promotion where advocacy mainly takes place at an internal organisation level and requires a large time commitment to achieve a positive outcome.

II. WHY WHY PRESERVE?

This landscape highlights the need for a comprehensive easy to access campaign that the sector as a whole can use to highlight the importance of both the work we do and why organisations should care about their own digital records.

A sector wide campaign allows everyone to work together towards a common goal, which will ease the advocacy burden currently felt by individuals tackling this task on their own. In addition, an ongoing campaign allows the community to collaborate and build up a bank of evidence to support those continuing to advocate and promote their work in digital preservation.

III. ABOUT THE CAMPAIGN

Why Preserve aims to be a high-level campaign, which, when combined with other DPC advocacy resources, will form a one stop shop for digital preservation practitioners requiring advocacy support. This campaign will be created and administered by the Digital Preservation Coalition but owned and added to by the global digital preservation sector. Why Preserve will run globally and will be designed to be used quickly and easily by anyone who needs to advocate for digital preservation as part of their role.

Why Preserve will encourage digital preservation practitioners at every level, all over the world to look at the reasons Why they do the work they do, but also Why their organisations need them to do this work. The campaign will help practitioners to identify these reasons and turn them into advocacy messages that can be used in a number of ways, internally and

externally to strengthen the case for digital preservation support and investment.

The campaign will include quick to digest statistics and data that show the importance of preserving digital content, combined with short quotes and statements from those both involved in, and who have benefited from the work. Short video and audio clips will also be included to increase accessibility. The aim is that anyone who needs to begin an advocacy conversation about digital preservation will be able to navigate to the Why Preserve online presence and immediately show their stakeholder a range of resources that highlight the importance of digital preservation. These resources will be accompanied by reflections from digital preservation practitioners stating what their work means to them.

IV. WHAT'S NEXT?

It is hoped that the Why Preserve resource will grow as awareness of the campaign grows. The DPC are also keen for the outputs of Why Preserve to be used to update the range of advocacy resources currently available, including the Executive Guide to Digital Preservation.

For the first time, iPRES 2025 coincides with World Digital preservation Day, which will result in a large number of digital preservation practitioners joining together in person and virtually to talk about our sector. We are hoping to use iPRES 2025 to raise awareness of the campaign amongst the digital preservation community and encourage participation. This alignment aims to amplify the campaign's impact and demonstrate how others can participate and contribute. This approach should also help ensure the legacy of iPRES 2025.

Community feedback on Why Preserve will be sought and acted upon at various review points throughout the creation and implementation of the project. Initial thoughts will be gathered at iPRES 2025, and further feedback will be collected as the campaign

⁶ Examples include, Baucom, E., Troup, T., Cote, C. & Mannheimer, S. (Winter 2017-18). Building strategic alliances to support advocacy and planning for digital preservation. *Journal of Digital Media Management*, 6(2), 182-194, and Rinehart, Amanda

K.; Prud'homme, Patrice-Andre; and Huot, Andrew R., "Overwhelmed to Action: Digital Preservation Challenges at the Under-resourced Institution" (2014). Faculty and Staff Publications - Milner Library. 51.

progresses. Collaboration will be key to the success of the campaign, and we are keen to involve as many organisations and practitioners as possible.

V. CONCLUSION

To truly make an impact, we must communicate the value of digital preservation in ways that resonate with diverse audiences. While its importance to truth, memory, and cultural heritage is undeniable, preservation is not just about safeguarding the past. For many organizations, it's also about managing risk, complying with legal and regulatory frameworks, protecting reputations, and ensuring business continuity. These practical drivers can be powerful catalysts for action. Being able to fully communicate this importance is a vital step in the advocacy workflow of every group and organisation working with digital records in a cultural heritage, research, academic, business and legal setting. It is hoped that the Why Preserve campaign will help digital practitioners across the world advocate both internally and externally for the importance of their work and the need for sustained support to carry it out.

VI. AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Karyn Williamson holds a master's degree in Archives and Records Management from the University of Dundee, a Post Grad Cert in Digital Information Management from University College Dublin and is a Registered Archivist. She is a Digital Preservation Analyst with the Digital Preservation Coalition and Campaign Manager for the Explore Your Archive Campaign.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to Angela Puggioni for her help and support in completing this article. Thank you to the DPC for providing the resources to make this campaign a reality.

